

ISic1659

I.Sicily inscription 1659

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ ἐνθά[δεκῖτεήκαλῆς]
2. μνήμης ἔ[ζησενἔτη]
3. Ξ Π Η ἐτ[ελεύτησεν]
4. ΑΥΓΣ ὑπ(ατία) Μ

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1989 with slight changes based on Orsi's 1896 edition

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645094

Bibliography

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